

Lightning Breakout 1 Room Assignments

- Breakout Room A (Glenn Assembly):
 - Mission-related software - part 1
- Breakout Room B (4W55):
 - Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Breakout Room C (2E39):
 - Infrastructure as code, and web and cloud applications - part 1
- Breakout Room D (2L78):
 - ML/AI codes - part 1
 - High performance computing - part 1
- Breakout Room E (2R69):
 - Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes) - part 1

Lightning Breakout 2 Room Assignments

- Breakout Room A (Glenn Assembly):
 - Mission-related software - part 2
- Breakout Room B (4W55):
 - Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)
 - General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)
- Breakout Room C (2E39):
 - Infrastructure as code, and web and cloud applications - part 2
 - Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)
 - Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)
- Breakout Room D (2L78):
 - ML/AI codes - part 2
 - High performance computing - part 2
- Breakout Room E (2R69):
 - Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes) - part 2